

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

It is my pleasure to announce the sixth regular issue of this year. Also this time, I thank all institutions and individuals - including the consortium members, members of the editorial board and authors - for their steady support and cooperation.

This issue covers 8 papers of various topics in computer science by authors from 10 countries. Iria Estévez-Ayres, Raquel M. Crespo-García, Jesús A. Fisteus, and Carlos Delgado Kloos from Spain discuss research on an algorithm for peer review in massive online courses. Doron Drusinsky from the USA introduces a novel behavioral and temporal pattern detection technique using diagrammatic, intuitive, yet formal specifications. In a collaborative work between Mexico and India, Juan Frausto-Solís, Mishael Sánchez-Pérez, Ernesto Liñan-García, Juan Paulo Sánchez-Hernández, and Manoj Ramachandran present an improved Simulated Annealing algorithm for the Protein Folding Problem (PFP). A personalized recommender system based on a hybrid model is introduced in a collaborative research paper by Wedad Hussein, Rasha M. Ismail, Tarek F. Gharib, and Mostafa G. M. Mostafa from Egypt and Saudi Arabia. Kun Ma and Runyuan Sun from China and Ajith Abraham from the USA introduce their research in cloud computing focusing on a module-centralized and aspect-oriented monitoring framework. Javier Marco, Sandra Baldassarri, and Eva Cerezo from Spain present in their paper the design process of a tangible game for very young children for the tabletop device NIKVision. In a collaborative research between UK and Germany, Javier Martínez Fernández, Juan C. Augusto, Giuseppe Trombino, Ralf Seepold, and Natividad Martínez Madrid tackle the negative influences of stress on individuals in the decision process in the finance market, and propose a system designed to support traders by providing them with information that can reduce the likelihood of poor decision-making. Finally, Karol Rástočný, Michal Tvarožek, and Maria Bielikova from Slovakia discuss in their contribution in information retrieval by introducing a Web search results exploration approach by cluster-based views and zoom-based navigation. Enjoy reading!

Cordially,

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